

Reactions of Benzotelluracyclopentane Diiodide

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Benzotelluracyclopentane diiodide (I) and the derivatives of the general formulae $C_6H_5TeX_2$ (X=halide, pseudohalide, carboxylate) and $[R_4N]^+[C_6H_5TeIX]^-$ (R=alkyl; X=halide) have been synthesized and characterized. I reacts with $Na_2S_9H_2O$ to give C_6H_5Te which undergoes oxidative addition reactions yielding C_6H_5TeXY (XY=halogen, interhalogen, organic halide, N-bromosuccinimide or benzamide) and molecular adducts with $HgCl_2$ and Cu_2Cl_2 . Te-C (alkyl) and Te-N bonds are readily cleaved by electrophiles. The elemental analysis, molar conductance, uv, ir, pmr and tga data are presented in support of the structure of newly synthesized compounds.

HETEROCYCLIC organotelluriums have recently been a subject of detailed investigation¹⁻⁶. In continuation to our studies on the chemistry of organometallic compounds of tellurium⁵⁻¹², we report the synthesis and reactivity of benzotelluracyclopentane diiodide under varying conditions.

Experimental

Materials and methods: α - α' -Dibromoxylene¹³, IBr^{14} (SCN)₂¹⁵ and $Cu_2Cl_2^{16}$ were prepared by the reported methods. Silver salts were freshly prepared before use. Tetraalkylammonium salts, mercuric chloride and iodine monochloride of BDH

grade were used. All the physico-chemical measurements were made as reported earlier⁶. TGA was recorded on an apparatus designed by Fertilizer Corporation of India.

(A) **Preparation of benzotelluracyclopentane diiodide (I):** Finely powdered tellurium metal (200 mesh) (2.54 g; 20 mmol), sodium iodide (12 g; 80 mmol) and α - α' -dibromoxylene (5.2 g; 20 mmol) in 2-methoxyethanol (~100 ml) were stirred at 100-110° for 2 hr. Addition of deionized water yielded an orange precipitate which was recrystallized with hot 2-methoxyethanol, washed with acetone (~15 ml) and dried *in vacuo* (yield=8.25 g; 85%).

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL DATA OF $C_6H_5TeX_2$

Compound $C_6H_5TeX_2$ X	Method	Colour (m.p.°C)	Analysis: Found (Calcd.)					Molar conductance (10 ⁻³ M soln in acetone) $\Lambda^{-1}cm^2mol^{-1}$
			Te	X	C	H	N	
I	A	Yellow orange (225d)	26.10	52.13	19.48	1.68	—	7.31
		Orange red (222d)	(26.28)	(52.27)	(19.79)	(1.66)	—	—
Cl	B	White (240d)	42.10	23.28	31.05	2.34	—	5.78
			(42.16)	(23.43)	(31.75)	(2.67)	—	—
Br	B	Yellow (219d)	32.36	40.50	24.34	2.08	—	4.96
			(32.59)	(40.81)	(24.54)	(2.06)	—	—
CN	B	White (140d)	45.00	—	42.05	2.66	9.67	6.31
			(44.96)	—	(42.32)	(2.84)	(9.87)	—
NCO	B	White (82d)	40.24	—	38.00	2.45	8.68	5.14
			(40.41)	—	(38.04)	(2.56)	(8.87)	—
NCS	B	White (117d)	36.23	—	34.42	2.15	8.00	8.45
			(36.68)	—	(34.52)	(2.32)	(8.05)	—
NCSe	B	Dark yellow (119)	28.95	—	27.09	1.77	6.16	7.71
			(28.90)	—	(27.20)	(1.83)	(6.34)	—
CH ₃ COO	B	White (168)	36.25	—	41.12	4.00	—	9.91
			(36.47)	—	(41.20)	(4.03)	—	—
CH ₃ CICOO	B	White (119-22)	30.42	—	34.28	2.69	—	9.25
			(30.47)	—	(34.42)	(2.89)	—	—
CF ₃ COO	†	White (159)	27.80	—	31.62	1.83	—	8.67
			(27.87)	—	(31.48)	(1.76)	—	—
C ₆ H ₅ COO	B	White (162)	26.85	—	55.52	3.91	—	7.31
			(26.92)	—	(55.75)	(3.83)	—	—

(B) *Preparation of benzotelluracyclopentane dichloride*: A solution of compound (I) (0.970 g; 2 mmol) in acetone (25 ml) was stirred with silver chloride (1 g; > 4 mmol). The insoluble silver salts were filtered off and the excess solvent distilled off under reduced pressure. On standing overnight in deep freeze, white crystalline benzotelluracyclopentane dichloride was obtained. It was washed with petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo* (yield=0.483 g; 80%).

(C) *Preparation of $[Et_4N]^+[C_8H_8TeI_2Cl]^-$* : A solution of compound (I) (0.970 g; 2 mmol) in acetonitrile (20 ml) was mixed with a solution of tetraethylammonium chloride (0.662 g; 4 mmol) in acetonitrile (20 ml). The mixture was refluxed for ~ 4 hr. The reaction mixture on concentration to crystallisation yielded the desired complex as a yellow solid. It was washed with petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo* (yield=1.066 g; 82%).

The experimental details, characterization data and exchange or addition reactions products are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

Preparation of benzotelluracyclopentane (II): A mixture of compound (I) (1.94 g; 4 mmol) and $Na_2S \cdot 9H_2O$ (15 g; ~ 60 mmol) was stirred at 100° for about an hour. The mixture was cooled and treated with crushed ice. A mixture of the desired product and unreacted tellurium was obtained. Its solvent ether extract containing the desired product was dehydrated with fused calcium chloride and used *in situ* for further reactions under nitrogen.

Oxidative addition reaction of organotelluride with methyl iodide: An ethereal solution of compound (II) (0.92g; 4 mmol) was mixed with methyl iodide (3 ml) and allowed to stand for 48 hr at room temperature. The mixture deposited a yellow crystalline solid which was separated and stored in fresh ether for ~ 12 hr.

 TABLE 2—EXPERIMENTAL DATA FOR $[R_4N]^+[C_8H_8TeI_2X]^-$

Compound $[R_4N]^+[C_8H_8TeI_2X]^-$	Method	Colour (m.p.°C)	Analysis : Found (Calcd.)%					Molar conductance (10 ⁻³ M Soln. in acetonitrile A ⁻¹ cm ⁻² mol ⁻¹)
			Te	I ₂ X	C	H	N	
Me Br	C	Orange (241)	19.90 (19.95)	52.08 (52.17)	22.48 (22.53)	3.08 (3.15)	2.03 (2.19)	173.50
Et Cl	C	Yellow (177)	19.05 (19.59)	44.30 (44.42)	29.36 (29.51)	4.05 (4.33)	2.02 (2.15)	150.87
Et Br	C	Yellowish orange (185)	18.18 (18.34)	47.52 (47.97)	27.55 (27.62)	4.00 (4.06)	2.00 (2.01)	144.58
Bu Br	C	Yellowish orange (202d)	15.40 (15.79)	41.90 (41.30)	35.40 (35.68)	5.32 (5.49)	1.58 (1.73)	177.95

TABLE 3—EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS OF BENZOTELLURACYCLOPENTANE DERIVATIVES

Reaction of C_8H_8Te with XY	Product	Reaction condition (time)	Solvent used in reaction	% Yield	Colour	m.p. (°C)
I ₂	$C_8H_8TeI_2$	r. temp. (1/2 hr)	Solvent ether	95	Orange	221 d
Br ₂	$C_8H_8TeBr_2$	0°C(1 hr)	"	90	Yellow	216 d
ICl	C_8H_8TeICl	~5°C(1 hr)	"	45	Dirty yellow	231
IBr	C_8H_8TeIBr	~5°C(1 hr)	"	85	Brownish yellow	212 d
(SCN) ₂	$C_8H_8Te(SCN)_2$	~20°C(3 hr)	Solvent ether and CCl ₄	66	White	118 d
*MeI	$C_8H_8Te \begin{matrix} Me \\ \\ I \end{matrix}$	r. temp. (48 hr)	Solvent ether	89	Yellow	214
	$C_8H_8Te \begin{matrix} Br \\ \\ O \\ \\ C \\ \\ N \\ \\ C \\ \\ O \end{matrix}$	r. temp. (2 hr)	Solvent ether and benzene	85	White	145
BrNHCOC ₂ H ₅	$C_8H_8Te \begin{matrix} Br \\ \\ NHCOC_2H_5 \end{matrix}$	"	"	83	White	125
HgCl ₂	$C_8H_8Te \cdot HgCl_2$	r. temp. (1/2 hr)	Solvent ether and water	95	White	185
Cu ₂ Cl ₂	$(C_8H_8Te)_2 \cdot Cu_2Cl_2$	"	Solvent ether and 1M HCl	90	Dirty white	165

Note : The observed elemental analysis are in close agreement with that of calculated values* 1 : 1 electrolyte (111.38 A⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) in DMF while others are non electrolytes.

Compound	Electrophile used	Product	Reaction condition (time)	Solvent used	% Yield	m.p. °C
C_8H_9TeMeI	I_2	$C_8H_9TeI_2$	r. temp. (2 hr)	Chloroform	80	218
	IBr	C_8H_9TeIBr	0°C (4 hr)	"	70	210
C_8H_9Te	Br_2	$C_8H_9TeBr_2$	r. temp. (2 hr)	CCl_4	70	212

It was then filtered, washed with solvent ether and dried *in vacuo* (yield=1.33 g; 89%). The experimental details are summarized in Table 3.

Addition reaction of organotelluride with metal halides: To an ethereal solution of compound (II) (0.92 g; 4 mmol) a saturated aqueous solution of $HgCl_2$ (1.09 g; 4 mmol) was added dropwise with constant stirring during $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The precipitated white solid was filtered and dried *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 (yield=1 g; 95%).

The product of reaction of Cu_2Cl_2 in 1M HCl with C_8H_9Te was isolated similarly.

Some cleavage reactions: In a representative experiment, a solution of IBr (0.414 g; 2 mmol) in chloroform (15 ml) was added dropwise to a solution of C_8H_9TeMeI (0.756 g; 2 mmol) in

chloroform (20 ml) at 0° till no more of it was decolourised. After complete addition, the solution was distilled off under reduced pressure and addition of excess petroleum ether yielded a brownish yellow product which was washed with petroleum ether and dried *in vacuo* and identified as $C_8H_9Te \begin{matrix} I \\ \diagdown \\ Br \end{matrix}$.

The relevant experimental details of cleavage reactions are summarized in Table 4.

Results and Discussion

The synthesis and reactivity of benzotelluracyclopentane diiodide were examined as follows. The benzotelluracyclopentane diiodide (I) is obtained by interaction of dibromoxylene with a mixture of tellurium metal and sodium iodide (reaction i):

The derivatives of compound (I) of the type $C_8H_9TeX_2$ are prepared by the following exchange reactions (ii) and (iii):

The trihalo anionic complexes of the type $[R_4N]^+[C_8H_9TeI_2X]^-$ are obtained as follows (iv):

The compound (I) reacts with $Na_2S \cdot 9H_2O$ to give C_8H_9Te [compound (II)] reaction (v):

The benzotelluracyclopentane, C_8H_9Te , undergoes several oxidative addition reactions yielding a number of hitherto unknown compounds (reaction vi):

[XY = I₂, Br₂, ICl, IBr, (SCN)₂, MeI, N-bromo-succinimide, N-bromobenzamide].

The telluride also reacts with metal halides and yields molecular adducts (reactions-vii) :

The cleavage of Te-C (alkyl) and Te-N bond in methyl benzotelluracyclopentane iodide and benzotelluracyclopentane bromide succinimide respectively occurs readily with I₂, IBr and Br₂ (reaction viii and ix) :

The Te-C bond in telluracyclopentane diiodide is stable towards halogens and pseudohalogens⁵. In the present investigation, the Te-C bond is readily cleaved in methyl benzotelluracyclopentane iodide by electrophiles XY'(XY'=I₂, IBr). The Te-N bond in benzotelluracyclopentane bromide succinimide is cleaved in preference to Te-C bond by Br₂.

Benzotelluracyclopentane diiodide and its derivatives are stable solids excepting diisothiocyanate, dicyanate and trifluoroacetate derivatives which slowly decompose on standing. They are soluble in common organic solvents and are unaffected by atmospheric oxygen and moisture.

The molar conductance (10⁻³M solution) data presented in Tables 1 and 2 indicate that organotelluriums of the formula $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{TeX}_2$ are non electrolytes while its trihalo anionic complexes possess 1 : 1 electrolytic nature. The conductance data in Table 3 indicate that all oxidative addition products are nonelectrolytes excepting $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{TeMeI}$ which is a 1 : 1 electrolyte in DMF.

IR spectra : In the ir spectra of benzotelluracyclopentane derivatives the $\nu\text{Te-C}$ invariably occurs around $\sim 550\text{ cm}^{-1}$, this position being similar to that in telluracyclopentane and telluracyclohexane derivatives^{4,5}. $\nu\text{Te-Cl}$ is identified at 282 cm^{-1} and is in agreement with the reported value for $\text{C}_4\text{H}_8\text{TeCl}_2^5$. $\Delta\nu\text{COO}=(\nu_{asym}\text{COO}-\nu_{sym}\text{COO})$ for diacetate, dimonochloroacetate, ditrifluoroacetate, dibenzoate are 345, 340, 405 and 298 cm^{-1} respectively which are in close agreement to the reported values for other organotellurium carboxylates^{8,9,18} having ester like structure. In almost all the carboxylates $\nu_{asym}\text{COO}$ undergoes splitting indicating non equivalence of the carboxylate groups^{8,18}.

In the newly synthesised chalcogenates NCX (X=O, S, Se), $\nu\text{C-X}$ appears at 1305, 862 and 610 cm^{-1} for X=O, S and Se respectively showing the pseudohalides groups¹⁹ in the *iso* form. In benzotelluracyclopentane dicyanide νCN at 2150 cm^{-1} suggests the presence of normal CN group in the compound^{4,5}.

The benzamide and succinimide derivatives show characteristic absorptions associated with $\nu_{asym}\text{CO}$ and $\nu_{sym}\text{CO}$ modes at 1688 ± 26 and 1290 cm^{-1} respectively²⁰.

¹H NMR spectra : ¹H NMR spectrum of benzotelluracyclopentane diacetate shows two singlets, one at 1.81 ppm due to methyl protons of acetate groups and the other at 4.36 ppm due to -CH₂-Te protons. The multiplet in the range of 7.33-7.0 ppm is attributed to four phenyl protons.

In the ¹H NMR spectrum of the complex anion $[(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_4\text{N}]^+ [\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{TeI}_2\text{Cl}]^-$ appearance of one multiplet in the range 7.33-7.0 ppm is due to phenyl protons and a quartet at 4.70-3.90 ppm is due to CH₂-Te protons. A triplet at 1.36-1.05 ppm and a quartet at 3.40-3.09 ppm are due to -CH₃ and -CH₂ protons of $[(\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2)_4\text{N}]^+$ respectively.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of methyl benzotelluracyclopentane iodide shows three signals, one as a sharp singlet at 2.44 ppm due to Te-CH₃ protons and a quartet at 5.10-4.10 ppm due to Te-CH₂ protons. The phenyl protons appear as a multiplet at 7.13 ppm.

The spectra and the integration correspond to the proposed stoichiometry of the compounds.

UV spectrum : The absorption band at 218 nm in the uv spectrum of $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{TeI}_2$ appears at almost identical position (211 nm) as in the spectrum of

C_8H_8Te ($OCOC_6H_5$)₂: It is attributed to $\pi-\pi^*$ benzoid transition²¹.

TGA analysis: The thermogravimetric curves of the two representative compounds $C_8H_8TeX_2$ ($X=OCOC_6H_5$; $OCOC_6H_5$) qualitatively show the following mode of decomposition. It starts at $200 \pm 20^\circ$ and at $700 \pm 20^\circ$, there is a residual mass corresponding to tellurium metal, which volatilises about above 800° .

Biocidal activity: The reaction products of exchange reaction and additions reaction were screened against different microorganism [*E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *M. tuberculosis*, *A. terreus*] and showed significant activity. The details of the results obtained will form the subject matter of another paper.

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